

Brewing Physics into Neural Networks: A PINN Approach to Newton's Law of Cooling

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Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) are neural networks that directly incorporate physical knowledge, typically expressed through differential equations, into the training process. Unlike a traditional Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), which relies solely on observed data, PINNs combine empirical information with physical laws to produce more accurate and consistent models, even in scenarios with limited or noisy data [2].

To illustrate the concept in an intuitive and slightly caffeinated manner, we consider the classic problem of coffee cooling, described by Newton's Law of Cooling [1]. This law models the temperature of a body over time through the ordinary differential equation:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = -r(T - T_{\text{env}}), \quad (1)$$

where T is the coffee temperature, T_{env} is the ambient temperature, and r is the cooling rate. The analytical solution of this ODE is given by:

$$T(t) = T_{\text{env}} + (T_0 - T_{\text{env}})e^{-rt}, \quad (2)$$

where T_0 is the coffee's initial temperature.

In our experiment, we generated synthetic data of coffee cooling from 90°C down to thermal equilibrium with an ambient temperature of 25°C, adding Gaussian noise to simulate real measurements. The MLP used had two hidden layers with 64 neurons each and was trained to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between predictions and data.

The PINN employed the same architecture, but its loss function included, in addition to the data loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$, a term penalizing violations of the physical equation (1) at collocation points:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + \lambda_{\text{phys}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}, \quad (3)$$

Where $\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$ corresponds to the residual of (1), and λ_{phys} controls the relative importance of the physics term in training.

The MLP had two hidden layers with 64 neurons and \tanh activations, trained with Adam (10^{-3} learning rate) and MSE loss. The PINN used the same setup but added a physics-based loss term. Model robustness was tested with 100 Monte Carlo runs, each starting from a different random seed (1-100). Thus, variability reflects only stochastic initialization and optimization, not additional data noise.

The results are summarized in Figure 1. Subfigure **a**) shows that although the MLP fits the noisy data, it presents higher uncertainty and deviates significantly from the analytical solution in the long run. In contrast, subfigure **b**) illustrates that the PINN not only adheres closely to the data but also respects the underlying physics, achieving a nearly perfect match with the analytical curve and displaying much lower variance.

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The comparison becomes even clearer in subfigures **c**) and **d**): while the MLP prediction (c) departs considerably from the analytical solution outside the training region, the PINN prediction (d) remains faithful to the expected exponential decay. Together, these results highlight the stabilizing role of physics in guiding the learning process.

In addition to temperature prediction, we also explored the use of the PINN for a physical regression problem: directly estimating the coffee’s cooling rate r . In this setup, r was treated as a trainable parameter, allowing the network to learn both the cooling curve and the physical value governing it. The physics loss remained based on equation (1), with collocation points used to compute the residual. Starting from a small initial guess for r , training converged to $r \approx 0.00468, s^{-1}$, very close to the true value $r_{\text{true}} = 0.005, s^{-1}$ used to generate the synthetic data. This result demonstrates that incorporating physics not only improves predictions but also enables the inference of hidden physical parameters from noisy data.

The coffee cooling example illustrates three key conclusions: (i) PINNs tend to outperform MLPs when reliable physical knowledge is available; (ii) the approach reduces the need for large data volumes; and (iii) in ill-conditioned problems, physics acts as a natural regularizer. On the downside, computational cost is generally higher, and correctly formulating the physics requires specialized knowledge of the phenomenon. Still, in our test, even a cup of coffee benefited from a small quantity of physics and let us face it, anything that helps coffee deserves attention.

The full implementation of the models and experiments presented in this work, including the training scripts and visualization routines, is publicly available on GitHub at: ⁵.

Figure 1. Results for the coffee cooling problem. **a**) MLP predictions compared with data and analytical solution, showing high variance and deviation. **b**) PINN predictions, closely aligned with both data and analytical solutions, with reduced variance. **c**) Direct comparison between MLP and the analytical solution. **d**) Direct comparison between PINN and the analytical solution, highlighting the accuracy of the physics-informed approach.

Referências

- [1] I. Newton. “Scala graduum caloris”. Em: **Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society** 22 (1701), pp. 824–829. DOI: [10.1098/rstl.1700.0050](https://doi.org/10.1098/rstl.1700.0050).
- [2] M. Raissi, P. Perdikaris e G. E. Karniadakis. “Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations”. Em: **Journal of Computational Physics** 378 (2019), pp. 686–707. DOI: [10.1016/j.jcp.2018.10.045](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2018.10.045).

⁵<https://github.com/Rogério97/pinns-with-pytorch-solving-the-heat-equation-for-a-cup-of-coffee>